

INVESTIGATING TYPE OF ISLAMIC INTEGRATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AT SMP YA BAKII 1 KESUGIHAN CILACAP

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Abstract: *This study was carried out to describe the types of Islamic integration taught in English Language Teaching in seventh grade Junior High School. In addition, the focus in this study is also to find out students' and teachers' responses related to English Language Teaching in seventh grade which is integrated with Islamic values. A qualitative descriptive research design was used in this study. The study involved one English teacher and six students of seventh grade. The type of integration in this study was proposed to Amin Abdullah. Based on the result of the study by interviewing and analyzing lesson plan, the researcher concluded that the type of integration carried out in English Language Learning was interconnected entities. In addition, based on the result of the students' and teachers' interview, students and teacher gave positive responses related to English learning which was integrated with Islamic values. English language teaching that integrated with Islamic values provided benefits and made students happy. In addition, students also got Islamic knowledge in learning and students feel not disturbed in understanding English lesson.*

Keywords: *Islamic Integration, English Language Teaching, Positive attitude*

INTRODUCTION

According to Norazmi (2013), she stated that integration is a process that can be implemented in the education part to create a civilized generation of multidisciplinary knowledge. In addition, Nufus (2016) stated that integration is defined as a corporation between two or more kinds of knowledge starting by the Islamic traditional knowledge of faith, morals, and worship. The understanding of Islamic values with modern world can lead to emersion of new modern knowledge in way with Islamic needs. Moreover, the school and teacher must have attention that the Islamic integration in learning and teaching process is needed by students.

ELT basically contains origin value and culture from its country. According to Zuliati (2012), she stated that the English teaching must bring the cultural content staying within the English language, whether the teacher includes cultural points in the purpose or not. In other opinion, Zuliati (2005) added that teachers have to teach the cultural points of certain language, because many linguistic symbols can not be interpreted without knowing the students' cultural contents. English language contains different culture and thought with Islamic value (Nufus, 2016). In this point, we can know that the teacher teaches the important role to select the western culture and thought in ELT which is not appropriate for students.

According to Kementrian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan (2013) stated that the standard competence of K-13 breaks down into the core competence. In the first core competence, it contains about the competence of religion or how students respect and apply the religion

theory. In the second competence, it contains about developing behaviour such as honesty, discipline, responsibility, care, well-behaved, environment awareness, mutual aid, politeness, self-confidence in the interaction with society and world effectively. The competence of religious and human behaviour were explained explicitly in the first core competence and the second core competence. Actually, the religious competence and the social competence are primary competences in ELT process.

In the context of English teaching, most of English teachers still think that the students background of Islamic knowledge is not too important to be uncovered in teaching and learning process (Elfi, 2016). The teachers only focus to the material and the topic being discussed that provided in many English books. They do not know about how to integrate the Islamic background knowledge of students in teaching English. According to Rahman (2017), he argued that it is a big problem, because the students will have attention about what they have seen, for instance the way the teachers’ taught. The target of ELT does not only make students have ability to communicate in English well but also have good character through the all instructional contents used by the teacher. In fact, the focus of teacher only use the instructional contents which is closely with western culture. The instructional contents did not give much contribution to build the students’ character.

Therefore, one way to overcome the problem is with integrating Islamic values in ELT to build students’ character. The integration of Islamic values in ELT hoped can build students’ Islamic character since they have much knowledge and experience relating to Islam. If students can share the idea related to Islamic knowledge in English, it can improve

both their English competence and their Islamic knowledge. Moreover, it can build students' character toward Islam.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of Educational Integration

Integration is an approach or process that can be used in educational area to create a madani generation of multidisciplinary knowledge (Norazmi et al, 2013). In addition, the concept of integration science and religion now refers to integration of science and Islam as unit (Norazmi et al, 2013).

According to Rashid (2013), he stated that an integrated knowledge is prominent in developing every aspect of human potentials and producing well-balanced being. Other, the development of mental, emotional, physical, and esthetic aspect can not be enhanced without the process of integration in the education system (Rashid, 2013). It is clear that education has a significant role in guiding human well-balanced though integrated education.

Based on the explanation above, it can be inferred that the Islamic integration as unit in learning and teaching is important. It can make civil society generations which applied the Islamic integration in students' life well.

Characteristic of Educational Integration

The form of integration has been discussed among scholars from time to time to make a proper model of education system included the developing types of integration. According to Ian Barbour (2002), he stated that integration is a relationship that based on belief which is

basically the study area, the design approach, and the purpose of science and religion are unite and same.

According to Nasekun (2015), he stated that here are some characteristic of educational integration;

1. Child-centered
2. Authentic
3. The separation between fields of study is not very clear.
4. Presenting concepts from various fields of study in a process Learning.
5. Flexible

The goal of Integration learning

According to PP no. 19 years old 2005 in Nasekun (2015), it stated that integration learning is not only developed to achieve goals holistic learning as stated in concerning National Education Standards, expected by students as well could:

1. Improve the understanding of concepts learned more meaningful.
2. Develop skills in finding, processing, and utilize information.
3. Develop positive attitudes, good habits and values noble needed in life.
4. Develop social skills such as cooperation, tolerance, communication, and respecting the opinions of others.
5. Increase passion in learning.
6. Have activities that are in accordance with interests and needs.

Types of Integration

The terms of integration has been discussed from time to time in creating ideal model. According to Nufus (2016), there are some types of integration as follow:

- 1) Ian G. Barbour

In his book, Ian stated the relationship between science and religion is one of typology. There are four relationships such as conflict, independence, dialogue, and integration.

a. Conflict between science and religion are conflicting relationship and in extreme cases even hostile.

b. Independence relationship means science and religion operate independently to their field, how, and their goals without disturbing each other or care.

c. Dialogue is relationship of mutual openness and respect, because both sides meant to understand their similarities and differences.

d. Integration is a relationship which based on belief that basically the study area, the design approach, and the purpose of science and religion are unite and same.

2) M. Amin Abdullah

Amin Abdullah reintegrates the epistemology of science based on the basic principles that need to be concerned. The areas were Hadarah Al-Nash (based on text), Hadarah Al-Ilm (scientific) and Hadarah Al-Falsafah (philosophy). The term of Hadarah Al-Nash can be equated with religion studies where the sources originating from revelation of Qur'an and Sunnah. While, Hadarah Al-Ilm refers to natural sciences and social sciences that acquired from senses, experiments, and logical laws. Then, Hadarah Al-Falsafah obtained from ethics and philosophy.

Amin Abdullah proposed interdisciplinary knowledge as the result of integration in some schema as follow:

a. The single entity of religion can be replaced with science or philosophy. This single entity has been claimed to be able to overcome

the problems of humanity with itself. The concept of single entity appeared arrogant because they feel the most proper one.

b. The isolated entities seem more advanced human civilization through the existence of the three fields. Although, the relationship’s configuration of this isolated model estimated as contemporary problems of crisis in living environment, economy, morality, religiousness, etc.

c. The interconnected entity is an ideal model. Each part was aware on their limitations. They are willing to engage in dialogue, cooperate and take advantage of methods and approach adopted by their sciences to complement each other.

Research Method

The research design in this study is descriptive qualitative research. According to Creswell (2009) stated that descriptive qualitative research is a means to export and understand the meaning individuals or groups to social or human problem. In additional, Sugiyono (2015) mentioned that in this study, the researcher defined research variable as “everything that is decided by researcher to be researched in getting information and finding out the conclusion.”

The study was conducted in seventh grader at SMP Ya BAKII 1 Kesugihan Cilacap. The research conducted at SMP Ya BAKII 1 Kesugihan Cilacap because the school have implemented the Islamic integration in English learning process. In addition, the school is the previous school of the researcher. Therefore, the researcher conducted the research in that school. This research was conducted on June-July 2020. The subject of the study are an English teacher and the students at seventh grade of SMP Ya BAKII 1 Kesugihan Cilacap. In this study, the researcher decided VII grade students as the subjects. This subject is decided by using purposed random sampling.

Result And Discussion

1. Types of integrating Islamic values in ELT at SMP Ya BAKII 1 Kesugihan Cilacap

According to the theory of Amin Abdullah in Nufus (2016), there are three types of integration. Integration is relationship which is based on belief that basically the study area, the design approach, and the purpose of science and religion are same and unite. It means that integration type did not make different between Islamic knowledge and science knowledge. While, Amin Abdullah stated that the interconnected entities are both of religion and science aware on their limitations. They are willing to engage in dialogue, cooperate and take advantage of methods and approach adopted by other sciences to complement each other's shortcomings.

Therefore, based on the analysis, the teacher has been implemented Islamic values in classroom activities. The teacher mostly delivered Islamic values by giving example, good advice, and daily activities that connected by worship. Based on the explanation above, the researcher concluded that the finding of interview and lesson plan analysis in accordance with the characteristics of integration or interconnected entity.

2. Students' and teachers' responses toward Islamic integration in ELT at SMP Ya BAKII 1 Kesugihan Cilacap

Based on the result of the findings, the students gave responds toward the Islamic integration in ELT. According to the questions that delivered to the six students, mostly the students gave responds that similar with other students. In addition, the students also gave responses that not related with the questions. The researcher believed that there are some reasons why students gave no related answer. First, the level of

questions that given to students and the students condition when they were interviewing. These are the students responds toward the Islamic integration in ELT when they were asked by question “Do you think that English lessons with material with Islamic values are fun and useful? If yes or no, give your reason.!”

1. Because they often recite Qur’an
2. Happy worship
3. Wash your hands often before eating

Based on the responses above, it can be concluded that the student did not understand dealing with question. The answer was not related with the questions. It caused of the level of question or the students condition while interviewing. The teacher should give proper material that related with the background of the students even he or she teaches science knowledge. Based on the responds above, the Islamic integration in ELT gave positive responds to the students.

Conclusion

A conclusion that can be derived in this research is that the type of integration used by teacher in English language teaching is interconnected entities proposed by Amin Abdullah. The Islamic values was given by teacher in every part of teaching. The teacher integrated Islamic values in science subject such as English. Science and religion needs each other. Then, the students gave positive responses toward the English teaching that integrated with Islamic values because there are two minimal students who give same responses. The Islamic values gave more benefits for students and made students fun in learning English. Other, the learning process that integrated with Islamic values in English teaching did not disturb students in understanding English material. However, students got more knowledge of Islam instead of learning English.

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